

Gulhayo MAMANAZAROVA,
Teacher, Uzbek State University of World Languages

Reviwer: DSc Paluanova Halifa Daribayevna Doctor of Philological Sciences

THE FALSE FRIENDS IN TRANSLATION IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES THROUGH THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

Annotation

In the article, we found out that the translator's false friends, a phenomenon that confuses the translator during the translation process, is a cross-linguistic phenomenon that arises as a result of the interaction of two related languages. These are the so-called homonyms and paronyms - pairs of words in two languages that are similar in spelling or pronunciation, often have a common origin, but differ in meaning. Such words can cause certain difficulties in translating the given text. "False friends" of the translator can be considered not only at the level of individual sentences and syntactic structures, but also at the level of phraseological units, in addition to individual words in the target language. The characteristics of each of them are considered in detail, and typical errors that may occur during translation are analyzed by direct examples. Based on this, recommendations were offered to help the translator avoid possible violations of the semantics of the translated text.

Key words: "False friends", phraseological units, text semantics, certain difficulties in translation.

RUS TILIDAN TARJIMA JARAYONIDA O‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA TARJIMONNING SOXTA DO‘STLARI

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada biz tarjima jarayonida tarjimoni chalg‘ituvchi hodisa tarjimonning soxta do‘stlari tillararo hodisa ikki turdosh tilning o‘zaro ta‘siri natijasida paydo bo‘lganligini aniqladik. Bular omonimlar va paronimlar deb ataluvchi – Ikki tildagi imlo yoki talaffuzda o‘xshash, ko‘pincha kelib chiqishi umumiy bo‘lgan, lekin ma‘no jihatidan farq qiladigan juft so‘zlardir. Bunday so‘zlar berilgan matn tarjima qilishda ma‘lum qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. Tarjimonning “soxta do‘stlari” tarjima qilinayotgan tildagi alohida so‘zlardan tashqari, alohida gaplar va sintaktik tuzilmalar darajasida, bundan tashqari, frazeologik birliklar darajasida ham ko‘rib chiqilishi mumkin. Ularning har birining xususiyatlari batafsil ko‘rib chiqiladi va tarjima paytida yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo‘lgan tipik xatolar bevosita misollar bo‘yicha tahlil qilinadi. Shundan kelib chiqqan holda, tarjimonga tarjima qilingan matn semantikasining mumkin bo‘lgan buzilishining oldini olishga yordam beradigan tavsiyalar taklif qilindi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Tarjimonning “soxta do‘stlari”, frazeologik birliklar, matn semantikasi, tarjima qilishdagi ma‘lum qiyinchiliklar.

ЛОЖНЫЕ ДРУЗЬЯ В ПЕРЕВОДЕ НА УЗБЕКСКИЙ И АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫКИ ЧЕРЕЗ РУССКИЙ ЯЗЫК

Аннотация

В данной статье мы выяснили, что ложные друзья переводчика, явление, сбивающее переводчика с толку в процессе перевода, является межязыковым явлением, вызванным взаимодействием двух родственных языков. Это так называемые омонимы и паронимы — пары слов в двух языках, сходные по написанию или произношению, часто имеющие общее происхождение, но различающиеся по значению. Такие слова могут вызвать определенные трудности при переводе данного текста. «Ложных друзей» переводчика можно рассматривать не только на уровне отдельных предложений и синтаксических конструкций, но и на уровне фразеологизмов, помимо отдельных слов в языке перевода. Подробно рассмотрены особенности каждого из них, а типичные ошибки, которые могут возникнуть при переводе, разобраны на прямых примерах. На основании этого были предложены рекомендации, помогающие переводчику избежать возможных нарушений семантики переводимого текста.

Ключевые слова: «Ложные друзья» переводчика, фразеологизмы, семантика текста, определенные трудности перевода.

Introduction. The political, economic, scientific, cultural cooperation of different peoples on a global scale is becoming increasingly stronger, and these relations cannot be imagined without translation. Today, talking about the importance of translation is like explaining the importance of the sun. That is, just as there is no life on earth without the sun, there is no communication between different peoples without translation, and there is no development without communication. "Ignorance of the life of other peoples, carelessness leads to national limitations". That is why translation is considered as a link that connects peoples, a tool that develops and enriches science and culture, a bridge that lays the foundation for mutual cooperation and solidarity. So, translation: - establishing friendship and cooperation between peoples; - accelerator of scientific and technical development; - the influence of culture, art and literature on each other; - plays an important role in the enrichment of languages. Translation is the re-expression of an idea expressed orally or in writing in a specific language using other language means.

Translation is derived from the word translator, and translator is derived from the Persian word tarzaban. It is known that the art of oratory was very developed among the peoples of Central Asia and Iran in ancient times. Speakers were called tarzaban. Tar means fresh, juicy, refreshing, delicate, gentle in Persian. Language means language. Tarzaban means an eloquent, a beautiful speaker, a master of words, a speaker of new and sharp words. Tarzabans, in addition to having deep knowledge, broad worldview, oratory skills, also knew several languages and used them in their speeches. After the arrival of the Arabs, they influenced social life, culture, science and other areas, and they also adopted many words and subjected them to the rules of the Arabic language. For example, the word tarzaban becomes "translator" (or "interpreter") in Arabic pronunciation. After that, it obeyed the word formation law of the Arabic language, and new infinitives (stems), verbs and nouns were formed from it. For example: tarujama, tirijama, tarjama, mutarjim, mutarjimu. Thus, tarjimon is the Arabic translation of the word tarzaban, and translation comes

from the word translator. A translator is a person who translates an oral speech or a written text in one language into another language, translator, interpreter, translator. Interpreting means translating, doing translation work. A professional horse. A translator is a specialist, a scientist dealing with the history, theory and criticism of translation. Translation studies is a science dealing with the theory, history and criticism of translation. In the past, translation, in addition to its current meaning, has expressed the meanings of explanation, explanation, interpretation of the text, interpretation, interpretation, and simple expression. For example, a biography is a description of the situation. Therefore, even until the beginning of the XX century, there was no clear boundary between the concepts of translation and commentary, translator and commentator, and one was used instead of the other. This is based on the form of translations and translation principles of translators. For example, the book "Shavqi Gulistan" written by Muradhoja ibn Salihhoja, published in 1909 at the "Ghulomiya" printing house, was both a translation and a review of the work "Gulistan" by Saadi Shirozi.

Discussions. The general theory of translation systematizes the conclusions derived from the concrete experience of translation and creates a basis for it. During the translation process, the results of the translation and its ideas are summarized, and the conditions and factors specific to the translation are taken into account in the translation activity. The concept of the general theory of translation was developed by the Russian linguist and linguist A.V. Fedorov's works are widely and fully covered. According to this concept, any quality translation text should begin with a philological analysis of its linguistic basis and end with an artistic creation or scientific editing.

Translation stages "The translation process consists of three stages:

- 1) perception of the original;
- 2) interpretation of the original;
- 3) restatement of the original.

The understanding of the original copy of the translator, who captures the work in order to translate it into his own language, takes place in three stages: in the first stage, the text is perceived literally, that is, philologically. At this stage, a number of translation errors may occur: mixing a word from another language with a word that sounds the same; falling into the trap of false equivalents in close languages; wrongly mastering the context, not understanding the meaning of some specific words; not understanding the author's content; in the second stage, attention is paid to methodological factors. A reader who has read the text correctly also understands the stylistic factors of linguistic expression, i.e. mood, pitch or tragic meaning, melodiousness or a tendency to dryly describe the story, etc. The official reader does not need to understand all these qualities, and the translator needs to determine and research how the author achieves the appropriate result. Translation requires a conscious attitude to the book with a much higher demand than ordinary reading; the third stage - from understanding the stylistic and semantic content of some language tools, the translator moves to understanding the artistic integrity of the work, the phenomenon of artistic reality, characters, their relationship, and the author's ideological intention. This way of understanding the text is very complicated and difficult - in order to fully perceive the artistic reality created by the author, the translator needs to have the power of wide observation. In order to fully grasp and understand the original, the translator must have the same imagination as, let's say, the director."

False friends of the translator (tracing from French faux amis), or interlingual homonyms are a pair of words in two languages that are similar in spelling and / or pronunciation, often with a common origin, but different in meaning.

For example, Polish. miasto - a city, not a place; czas - time, not hour, eng. angina - стенокардия, not tonsillitis, genial - kind, not brilliant, magazine - a journal, not a store; English and Spanish mosquito is a mosquito- комар.

False friends of the translator can lead to misunderstanding and mistranslation of the text. Some of them were formed due to the fact that after borrowing the meaning of the word in one of the languages changed, in other cases there was no borrowing at all, and the words come from a common root in some ancient language, but have different meanings; sometimes the consonance is purely coincidental. The term "false friends" was introduced by M. Kössler and J. Derocchigny in 1928 in the book "Les faux amis ou Les pieges du vocabulaire anglais".

A particular case of the translator's false friends are pseudo-internationalisms - interlingual homonyms associated (in their graphic and / or phonetic form) with words of international vocabulary and causing all sorts of difficulties in translation: complete or utterances, violation of lexical compatibility or stylistic agreement of words in the utterance.

In contrast to the translator's false friends, there are also words that in the two given languages have the same meaning and similar sound. Such "friends of the translator" are called lexical cognates.

Arguments that arise as a result of using words that do not correspond to each other in the translation, believing that the form and spelling of the original and translated languages are similar. For example, the English word actual means актуальный in Russian. If you trust the Uzbek word actual (dolzarb), you will find a false friend. Some words may correspond phonetically to words in other languages or be very similar to them, but their content and meanings differ significantly from each other. For example, the English word Academic means a highly educated person, a student, a teacher of a higher school, in Russian and Uzbek it is used in the academic sense of a real member of the Academy of Sciences. Words that are similar in form but have significantly different meanings are called false equivalents.

In the practice of translation, another type of "false friends" remains unsystematized and unexplored, where the cause of the error is not the word, but the whole statement misunderstood by the translator, as a result of which it makes sense to think about whether the concept of "false friend" can be extended to the level of the structure of the statement. The structure of statements such as You can't be too careful or I don't think much of him can lead the translator's thought on the wrong path. Indeed, it is possible to make a mistake and translate them respectively as «Нельзя быть слишком осторожным» (instead of the correct version "Excessive caution does not hurt") and «Я не так много о нём думаю» (instead of "I don't think much of him"). In the last example, the idea is expressed in a very complicated way for Russian linguistic thinking that under the indicated condition, no matter how careful you are, it will never be "слишком". That is, you are advised to be as careful as possible. At the heart of the English utterance is a special emphasis on the concept of "too". The concept of "enough" can also play the same role, with the help of which a variant of a "false friend" is created. For example, the English hostess of the house is tired of overstaying guests, and she can say the following phrase: They cannot go fast enough. I mean, no matter how soon they leave, it won't be fast enough for her. It's not that the guests do not know how to move, but simply behind this "false friend" is a wish: "I wish they left, "Скорее бы они ушли" Of course, an experienced translator knows that a public house is not a "публичный дом", but just a British kind of beer hall, and a public school is not a public at all, but, on the contrary, a privileged private school in Britain. However, he may also be puzzled by an English statement like: I am satisfied that I alone am guilty of the disaster, since in many cases he

translated the expression to be satisfied “быть удовлетворенным, довольным” and did not meet it in the meaning “to be convinced, confident”. Often the translator is let down by statements with conjunctions and prepositions well known to him. They are usually ambiguous and can denote different relationships between significant words (for example, as can be a union of time, reason, comparison). Here is the phrase: "He was as liberal with his money as any other officer in the British army." It would seem that this should mean that all English officers are distinguished by the same generosity as the one in question. In fact, it means that he was not inferior in generosity to any of them. In extreme cases, you can call it “one of the most”, but the as...any structure seems to be intended for the translator to decide that we are talking about the universal equality of some attribute. We know that good is “хорошо”, but as good as does not mean at all a comparison of two positive signs, but can simply express the equality or similarity of any signs - positive or negative. In some cases, as good as actually means as bad as—for example, in the saying a miss as good as a mile, which states that missing a little is no better than missing a mile. Curiously, as bad as by itself is not used to denote simple equality, and in all cases bad is bad. Phraseological units can also be called “false friends” in those cases when they cause erroneous, false associations of both phraseological and non-phraseological nature. The English expression more dead than alive, sometimes erroneously translated as neither alive nor dead, actually means a state of extreme fatigue. Phraseologism to pull the devil by the tail (to be in a quandary, in cramped circumstances) can send the Russian reader, who is trying to rely on his inner form, on the wrong track. This phrase, by analogy with the Russian

expressions “to hold God by the beard” or “to catch the firebird by the tail”, can be erroneously interpreted almost in the opposite sense (“to be the master of the situation”, “to be lucky”). The image underlying the English idiom a heart of oak can also lead to false associations associated with the idea of spiritual deafness, callousness or even cruelty of a person. In reality, the idiom has a definitely positive appraisal and characterizes a person as brave, courageous, courageous. Having met a steady turn to pass the time of the day, an inattentive translator can take the easiest path and, by analogy with Russian, which formally resembles its “соответствием”, convey it as “проводить время, проводить день”, especially if the context does not have a there are no contraindications to this, as, for example, in the sentence: He was passing the time of the day with one of his secretaries.

Each has its own characteristics and creates certain difficulties for the translator when interpreting the text. Using specific examples, we compared and systematized possible errors in the translation of this category of words. Relevant recommendations have been drawn up in detail to help avoid "pitfalls" when meeting with "false friends".

Conclusion. Translation is undoubtedly a very ancient form of human activity. In translation practice, there is the concept of translation difficulties. One of the components of this concept is “false friends of the translator”, — an interlingual phenomenon that has been sufficiently studied in the translation literature, but, nevertheless, is of particular interest to translators and linguists. After all, this category of words can mislead even experienced translators who speak the language at a high level, leading to possible distortions of meaning in translation.

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